

THE INFLUENCE OF TEAMWORK AND WORK DISCIPLINE ON THE PERFORMANCE OF EMPLOYEES OF THE OPERATIONAL DIVISION OF PT MUSTIKA ALAM LESTARI TANJUNG PRIOK, NORTH JAKARTA

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Abstract

The Effect of Teamwork and Work Discipline on Employees of the Operational Division of PT Mustika Alam Lestari Tanjung Priok, North Jakarta, employee performance problems must be resolved, the purpose of this study is to determine the effect of cooperation on employee performance, the effect of work discipline on employee performance and the simultaneous effect of cooperation team and work discipline on employee performance, quantitative research methods with descriptive approaches used to describe more informative data, random sampling techniques to determine the sample of this study as many as 68 respondents, the results of this study indicate that teamwork as a joint effort in achieving work goals in one operational division so as to achieve performance, as evidenced by the results of this study that there is an effect of teamwork (X1) on employee performance (Y) of 0.597 or 35.64%. Work discipline as a limit to employee behavior in carrying out work that must be achieved by work not from so that it can achieve employee performance, as evidenced by the results of research that the effect of work discipline (X2) on employee performance (Y) is 0.745 or 55.5% and there is the effect of cooperation team (X1) and work discipline (X2) simultaneously on employee performance (Y) of 56.85%.

Keywords: Teamwork, work discipline and employee performance

Abstrak

Pengaruh Kerjasama Tim Dan Disiplin Kerja Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan Divisi Operasional PT Mustika Alam Lestari Tanjung Priok Jakarta Utara, permasalahan kinerja karyawan harus diselesaikan, tujuan penelitian ini untuk mengetahui pengaruh Kerjasama tim terhadap kinerja karyawan, pengaruh disiplin kerja terhadap kinerja karyawan dan pengaruh simultan Kerjasama tim dan disiplin kerja terhadap kinerja karyawan, metode penelitian kuantitatif dengan pendekatan deskriptif digunakan untuk menggambarkan data yang lebih informatif, tehnik random sampling untuk mengetahui sampel penelitian ini sebanyak 68 responden, hasil penelitian ini menunjukkan bahwa Kerjasama tim sebagai upaya Bersama-sama dalam mencapai tujuan kerja dalam satu divisi operasional sehingga mencapai kinerja, terbukti dengan hasil penelitian ini bahwa terdapat pengaruh Kerjasama tim (X1) terhadap Kinerja karyawan (Y) sebesar 0,597 atau 35,64%. Disiplin kerja sebagai batasan perilaku karyawan dalam melaksanakan pekerjaan yang harus dicapai dengan pekerjaan yang bukan dari tugasnya sehingga dapat mencapai kinerja karyawan, terbukti dengan hasil penelitian ini bahwa pengaruh Disiplin kerja (X2) Terhadap Kinerja karyawan (Y) sebesar 0,745 atau 55,5% dan terdapat pengaruh simultan Kerjasama tim (X1) dan Disiplin kerja (X2) secara simultan terhadap Kinerja karyawan (Y) sebesar 56,85%.

Kata kunci : Kerjasama tim, Disiplin kerja dan Kinerja karyawan

تجريدي

تأثير العمل الجماعي وانضباط العمل على أداء الموظف في القسم التشغيلي في بي تي موسيكا علام ليستاري تانجونج بريوك شمال جاكرتا ، يجب حل مشاكل أداء الموظف ، والغرض من هذه الدراسة هو تحديد تأثير العمل الجماعي على أداء الموظف ، وتأثير انضباط العمل على أداء الموظف والتأثير المتزامن للعمل الجماعي وانضباط العمل على أداء الموظف ، وتستخدم طرق البحث الكمي ذات النهج الوصفي لوصف بيانات أكثر إفادة وتقنيات أخذ عينات عشوائية لمعرفة عينة من هذه الدراسة تصل إلى 68 مستجيبا ، تظهر نتائج هذه الدراسة أن العمل الجماعي كجهد مشترك في تحقيق أهداف العمل في قسم تشغيلي واحد وذلك لتحقيق الأداء ، كما يتضح من نتائج هذه الدراسة أن هناك تأثير للعمل الجماعي (X1) على أداء الموظف (Y) بنسبة 0.597 أو 35.64٪. انضباط العمل كقيد لسلوك الموظف في القيام بالأعمال التي يجب تحقيقها بعمل ليس من واجباته وذلك لتحقيق أداء الموظف ، فقد ثبت من خلال نتائج هذه الدراسة أن تأثير انضباط العمل (X2) على أداء الموظف (Y) هو 0.745 أو 55.5٪ وهناك تأثير متزامن للعمل الجماعي (X1) وانضباط العمل (X2) في وقت واحد على أداء الموظف (Y) بنسبة 56.85٪. الكلمات المفتاحية: العمل الجماعي والانضباط في العمل وموظفي كينرج

INTRODUCTION

Tanjung Priok has long been an icon of North Jakarta, Tanjung Priok as a symbol of an intermodal sea port, where the Dutch colonial period mentioned that Tanjong Priok not only has a port, but as an icon of ship berthing traffic which only began to help colonial Batavia until now it is the busiest port in Indonesia. It is also undeniable that Tanjong Priok has become the center of queues and many kinds of crowded activities, one of which is the queue of passengers and goods from and boarding ships at Tanjung Priok Port.

PT Mustika Alam Lestari which is located at Jalan Bitung Ujung No.1, Tanjung Priok Port DKI Jakarta is a company engaged in providing port services for international trade. The scope of services includes delivery, receiving, behandle, monitoring of reefer, and stevedoring activities.

Since 2004, PORT through PT Mustika Alam Lestari has managed the T300 dock at Tanjung Priok Port with productivity reaching 65 boxes per ship operating hour. One problem at Tanjung Priok port is congestion caused by the length of container processing at the port. Dwelling time at Indonesia's largest port as of March 2018 is still at 3.45 days, not in accordance with the wishes of President Joko Widodo who wants Dwelling Time under 3 days (Pitoko, 2018).

Figure 1 proportion of Tanjung Priok per polling station

In the role of Port activities in Tanjung Priok is always connected with some operational divisions in activities carried out by companies both companies under the auspices of the government and private, private companies that have a role in the ups and downs of passengers and goods commonly known as ship companies, especially PT Mustika Alam Lestari (MAL).

However, in the operational division covering PT MAL's daily activities which are indeed very dependent on the human resources (HR) in it, duties and responsibilities become the main basis of work for PT MAL's human resources, therefore, HR coordination is always strictly applied, especially regarding its performance, this is because it is illustrated by PT MAL's mission to provide efficient ship loading and unloading services and container stacking to increase the competitiveness of service users port. This means that services provided directly can only be seen from work behavior or performance.

If, there is no performance from HR (employees) it can be said that there is no complete service effort, if the receipt of goods invoices enters the system, only with employees who carry out loading and unloading neatly and meet the demands of customers. So that the importance of performance is always demanded to be achieved. Conversely, if the absence of daily employees will complicate distribution and the length of the loading and unloading process in accordance with the invoices recorded, the daily processing time can be seen in the following figure:

Figure 2 Containerized Process Data Distribution at TPS

In the picture, it can be seen that the duration of container distribution is an issue that causes problems for the company, meaning that the problems felt by the company must return to employee performance. Because humans are the wheel of daily activities for goods and queues that enter the Port shipping system by handling high queue problems.

Sinambela, et al (2012) suggest that employee performance is defined as the ability of employees to do certain skills. Employee performance is very necessary, because with this performance it will be known how far the employee's ability to carry out the duties assigned to him. For this reason, it is necessary to determine clear and

measurable criteria and set together which are used as a reference. This means that with the joint implementation of duties and responsibilities, employees who are recorded as workers at PT MAL must achieve performance with clear and measurable results, but the achievement of employee performance is not only by chance but together.

Employee performance is not always achieved individually but sometimes different from the expected intended results of the tasks carried out such as new problems at work that cannot be denied there will always be mistakes, because not all employees are able to work together, there are even workers who are more active themselves in completing their work, but workers who have different behaviors will impose the objectives of the company's mission that hire him. Employee performance can come from factors that affect performance, this factor is what sometimes makes employee work behavior different. If the behavior of workers in carrying out work is always equal and there is no difference, it is wrong and it is a kind of printing work done by machines, meaning the same print, but different from employees as humans who have the power to create better work results, there are even humans in working not to correct mistakes and far from the expectations of the company's mission goals.

Proven by Vallenia, Atikah and Azijah (2022) which shows that based on the results of their research, work discipline factors have a positive and significant effect on employee performance with the results of the Coefficient of Determination test showing a magnitude of 21.9%, meaning that it is proven that performance can be influenced by factors that influence it such as work discipline. Thus, it is said by Setiawan (2019) that discipline grows from the need to maintain a balance between agility and individual desire to act accordingly and can be obtained or because of certain conditions with necessary regulatory restrictions on themselves and the environment in which they live. This means that performance derived from the influence of disciplinary factors has a tendency and balance to act in accordance with the acquisition or because of conditions that are limited by rules against the employees themselves. Conversely, if there are no company rules that do not limit employees in the implementation of work and their duties are increasingly uncontrollable and will certainly differ from the expectations that want to be produced with employees working, so that weak discipline will have an impact on weak employee performance. This is certainly not desired by the company, especially in the work of loading goods onto ships at the port.

Furthermore, Akbar (2018) empirically said that good labor management will be able to create an optimal working atmosphere in order to realize labor productivity in the organization. There are many factors that can affect employee performance at work. Then it was empirically proven by Ibrahim, Djuhartono and Sodik (2021) that there was a positive and significant influence of teamwork on employee performance from the calculated value of $7.77 > \text{table } 2.01$. This indicates that the better the implementation of teamwork carried out by the company, the more employee performance will increase. This means that the factor that affects employee performance that is no less important is teamwork on employee performance.

According to Paris, Salas and Bower (2020) that teamwork is a group of individuals who are together or a combination of the behavior of several individuals who have abilities, skills and work behaviors which are then shown to support team members together to achieve work goals. But it is different if individuals do not want to cooperate and even get used to working separately and alone, then employee performance will not be achieved, besides that performance that does not work together is still weak to achieve work goals. Weak employee performance still has an impact on not achieving the company's mission, this is where performance problems still need research so that clear identification of the problem is visible. Therefore, it is important to conduct team work research on employee performance so that it can prevent problems in the future.

LITERATURE REVIEW

1. Definition of Teamwork

According to Susanti, Widyani, and Utami (2021: 226), teamwork is a system of combining group work supported by various expertise with clarity of purpose, and also supported by leadership and communication to produce higher performance than individual performance. While Panggiki, Lumanauw, and Lumintang (2017: 3019) define teamwork as a form of work in groups that must be organized and managed properly. Teams of people who have different skills are coordinated to work closely with the leadership. There is a strong interdependence on each other to achieve a goal or complete a task.

Bachtiar (2104: 7) that "Cooperation is the synergy of the strengths of several people in achieving one desired goal. Cooperation will bring together the power of ideas that will lead to success." According to Burn (2014) a team is a work group consisting of several people with equivalent competencies, where they work dependently in carrying out work in one organization. The definition of teamwork is a group of people who work together to achieve the same goal and these goals will be easier to obtain by doing teamwork than done alone (Lawasi and Triatmanto, 2017)

From the various definitions above, it can be concluded that teamwork is a group of people with different abilities, talents, experiences and backgrounds who gather together to achieve one goal in one or more activities.

2. Understanding Work Discipline

Discipline comes from the Latin Discere which means to learn. From this word arises the word Disciplina which means teaching or training. But now the word discipline is undergoing a development of meaning in several senses. First, discipline is defined as compliance with regulations or submission to supervision, and control. Second, discipline as an exercise aimed at developing oneself in order to behave in an orderly manner. While broadly discipline can be interpreted as a kind of influence designed to help children to be able to face environmental demands (Majid, 2020).

Latainer in Sutrisno (2019: 87) defines "discipline as a force that develops in the body of employees and causes employees to adjust voluntarily to decisions, regulations, and high values of work and behavior.

In various places and circumstances, discipline is a very important thing to have. Especially if the context is an organization or educational institution, because discipline is very important for the growth of an organization, discipline is used to provide habituation to the processing of educational institutions so that later they can be ingrained in each individual in carrying out the trust given by the institution. In addition, discipline provides great benefits for the world of education in this case is to like the rules, procedures, and policies that have been determined by the institution and produce students who have good behavior and behavior.

According to Nitisemita (2019: 199): "Work discipline is an attitude, behavior and actions that are in accordance with the regulations of the company both written and unwritten". According to Atmosudirjo in Wursanto (2015; 146) "Labor discipline is obedience to the institution or organization and all that is stipulated without using feelings, based only on conversion and awareness that without such obedience everything that is stipulated in the organization's goals is not achieved. In work discipline, there is a willingness to live up to the rules, norms, laws and regulations that apply so that they will consciously implement and obey them.

From the definition above, it can be concluded that work discipline is an attitude of willingness and willingness of a person to obey and obey the applicable regulations, both written and unwritten and able to carry them out and not avoid receiving sanctions if he violates the duties and authorities given to him. The purpose of discipline both in groups and individually is to direct one's behavior to a harmonious reality and to create these conditions, there must first be an acceleration between the rights and obligations of employees.

3. Understanding Employee Performance

According to Hasibuan (2017: 94), employee performance is a result of work achieved by a person in carrying out his duties imposed on him which is based on ability, experience and sincerity and time. According to Fahmi (2020: 188) "Performance is the result of a process that refers to and is measured over a certain period of time based on predetermined terms or agreements". Meanwhile, according to Mangkunegara (2017: 9) states that performance is the result of work in quality and quantity that can be achieved by an employee in carrying out duties in accordance with the responsibilities given to him.

Based on some of the theories above, it can be concluded that performance is a general term that is used in part or all of the actions or activities of an organization in a period with a reference. Performance as a result of employee work is seen from aspects of quality, quantity, working time, and cooperation to achieve the goals set by the organization. Performance is the output produced by the functions or indicators of a job or a profession in a certain time.

METHOD

The research method used is quantitative. Quantitative deals with numbers. This descriptive method involves collecting data to test hypotheses or answer questions about people's opinions on an issue or topic. Quantitative research is research based on collecting and analyzing data in the form of numbers (numeric) to explain, predict, and control phenomena of interest. Quantitative research emphasizes its analysis on numerical data processed by statistical methods. With quantitative methods, the significance of relationships between variables will be obtained.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The location in this study is at PT Mustika Alam Lestari. The results of the research hypothesis show that it is proven that there is a significant positive influence on each variable and together Teamwork (X1) and Work Discipline (X2) simultaneously on the performance of employees (Y) of PT MAL's operational division at Tanjung Priok port, North Jakarta. In the discussion of this study, it is stated that there are factors that affect employee performance (Y), as follows:

1. Discussion of Hypothesis 1 Test Results

The effect of teamwork (X1) on employee performance (Y)

The results of the first hypothesis test show that there is a proven effect of teamwork (X1) on employee performance (Y). At a calculated value of 2.973. with Ttable (0.678) with $df\ 68 - 2 = 66$. So accept H1 shows that there is an effect of teamwork (X1) on employee performance (Y) by accepting H1 and rejecting H0. Thus the first hypothesis was proved.

The acquisition of an R square value of 0.934 which means that the effect of teamwork (X1) on employee performance (Y) is 0.597 or 35.64%. And the remaining 64.36% was influenced by other variables that were not studied in this study such as work facilities.

The results of this study are in accordance with research conducted by Darmanto (2016) The purpose of this study is to analyze the effect of teamwork on employee performance. The respondents of the study were 137 employees of the Independent Business Unit of the Brumbung Wood Industry Perum Perhutani Unit I Central Java. Data analysis using Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) with the help of AMOS v. 4.0 and SPSS v. 16 programs. In line with Farhan Elang Ibrahim, Tjipto Djuhartono and Nur Sodik who showed that there is a positive and significant influence of teamwork on the performance of PT. Lion Superindo can be proven from the calculated value of $7.77 > \text{table } 2.01$. This indicates that the better the implementation of teamwork carried out by the company, the more the performance of employees at PT. Lion Superindo. The implication of the results of this study is that to improve employee performance can be done by improving good and effective teamwork, such as increasing enthusiasm at work, reducing work conflicts, and improving relationships between groups.

2. Discussion of Hypothesis 2 Test Results

The effect of work discipline (X2) on employee performance (Y).

The results of the first hypothesis test show that there is a proven influence of work discipline (X2) on employee performance (Y). At the value, $t_{\text{calculate}}$ is 3.119. with T_{table} (0.678) with df $68 - 2 = 66$. So accept H_1 shows that there is an influence of work discipline (X2) on employee performance (Y) by accepting H_1 and rejecting H_0 . Thus the second hypothesis was proved. The acquisition of an R value of 0.745 which means that the effect of work discipline (X2) on employee performance (Y) is 0.745 or 55.5%, and 44.5% is influenced by other variables that are not studied in this study such as job training and work facilities.

The results of this study are in accordance with the results of research conducted by Devy Dayang Septiasari (2017) showing the Influence of Work Discipline on Employee Performance at the Department of Industry, Trade, Cooperatives, Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises of East Kalimantan Province in Samarinda. Research Methods This type of research uses data analysis, namely multiple linear regression, correlation coefficient, determination coefficient and partial test. In the same direction as

Kirana Vallennia, Atik Atikah and Fitri Nur Azijah who showed that the resulting regression equation showed that work discipline had a positive and significant effect on the performance of PT. Sinar Sosro Rancaekek. The coefficient of determination shows the magnitude of the influence of work discipline on the performance of PT. Sinar Sosro Rancaekek 21.9% while the rest is influenced by factors other than work discipline. The calculation results show a fairly small percentage of work discipline to employee performance is only 24.9%, so other factors are believed to have a major influence in influencing employee performance and need to be reviewed. This study concluded that work discipline has a significant influence on the performance of PT employees. Sinar Sosro Rancaekek.

3. Discussion of Hypothesis 3 Test Results

The Effect of Teamwork (X1) and Work Discipline (X2) Simultaneously on Employee Performance (Y).

The results of the fourth hypothesis test show that there is a proven simultaneous influence of teamwork (X1) and work discipline (X2) simultaneously on employee performance (Y). In the anova table test F because $F_{\text{calculate}} = 42.818 > F_{\text{table}} = 2.74$. So H_0 was rejected and H_1 was accepted. So it can be concluded that the simultaneous effect of teamwork (X1) and work discipline (X2) simultaneously on employee performance (Y) is significant and positive. Furthermore, the R square value of 0.754 or 56.85% means that there is a simultaneous influence of teamwork (X1) and work discipline (X2) simultaneously on employee performance (Y) by 56.85%, and other values of 43.14% are influenced by other variables that are not studied in this study such as job performance, work skills and leadership styles as well as others.

The results of this study are in accordance with the results of previous research conducted by Jeni Nata Liyas and Reza Primadi (2017) showing the Influence of Work Discipline on Employee Performance at People's Credit Banks. Factors that affect performance according to Siagian (2002) states that employee performance is influenced by several factors, namely: compensation, work environment, organizational culture, teamwork, leadership, and work motivation, work discipline, job satisfaction, communication and other factors.

CONCLUSION

Based on the discussion of research results for the conclusion of this study, researchers compile into three conclusion points.

1. Teamwork as a joint effort in achieving work goals in one operational division so as to achieve performance, it is proven by the results of this study that there is an influence of teamwork (X1) on employee performance (Y) of 0.597 or 35.64%.
2. Work discipline as a limitation of employee behavior in carrying out work that must be achieved with work that is not from their duties so as to achieve employee performance, it is proven by the results of this study that the effect of work discipline (X2) on employee performance (Y) is 0.745 or 55.5%
3. Performance as a result of work that has been achieved by employees jointly and individually so as to maximize the performance of the employees themselves, it is proven that the factors that affect performance come from teamwork and discipline, it is proven that there is a simultaneous influence of teamwork (X1) and work discipline (X2) simultaneously on employee performance (Y) by 56.85%.

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